

Awareness on Employment Registration in Coimbatore City - A Study

Dr.M.Kalimuthu

Associate Professor in Commerce

Dr. N. G. P. Arts and Science College, Coimbatore

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 3

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Kalimuthu, M.

“Awareness on

Employment

Registration in

Coimbatore City-A

Study.” *Shanlax*

International Journal of

Commerce, vol. 7,

no. S3, 2019, pp. 61–71.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572427)

[zenodo.2572427](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572427)

Introduction

Labour is the key factor for the growth of any economy and is of particular importance in the developing economies as these economies primarily depend on human force for development. Therefore, the growth by way of gainful employment of the labour is essential for the sustainable development. India is no exception to this phenomenon. After independence creating employment was an important aspect for the government and policy planners.

Employment Exchanges play a significant role in assisting the youth in finding employment in paid jobs. Registering the applications of job-seekers and notifying them about vacancies, collection and dissemination of Employment Market Information, Vocational Guidance to students and the youth are the major functions of Employment Exchanges.

Employment exchanges are responsible for collecting regularly information about employment in the Private Sector as well as in the Public Sector. This is being done by what is known as ‘establishment reporting’ system. The Employment Exchanges (Compulsory Notification of Vacancies) Act, 1959 was enacted to provide for compulsory notification of vacancies to the Employment Exchanges and for performance of returns by the employers (regarding both employment and vacancies).

Need for Awareness for Employment Registration is important because unemployment has been described as the most significant sociological problem in society. Unemployment occurs when a person who is actively searching for employment is unable to find work. Unemployment is often used as a measure of the health of the economy. For many of us the idea of unemployment is one of those who do not have a job or paid no salary. This is partly correct but not wholly. Such an impression would apply largely to the educated people who are not able to find work or to those in urban areas who come to seek employment.

Unemployment has thus reached such an alarming situation today that is perhaps considered the most serious of the problem affecting India and one that is steadily worsening as the gap between the rapid rising member pressing for work and the new employment opportunities being created widen.

Statement of the Problem

Our study proposes to investigate several problems faced by the students and public who are unemployed after the studies either they are passed or failed. Many students and public are lacking awareness for the employment registration like

- When can it be done?
- Where can it be done?
- How can it be done? etc.,

This study is to create awareness about the employment registration for the students and also public in Coimbatore city.

Objective of the Study

- To know about the performance of Employment Exchange in Coimbatore city.
- To create awareness among the students and public about the Employment Registration.
- To undertake a survey regarding the problems faced in Employment Registration.

Research Methodology

The study is based on the primary data and secondary data. The data collected are tabulated and analyzed in such a way to make interpretations.

Data Collection

The primary data for the survey is been collected by distributing questionnaire to the students and public in Coimbatore city, while the secondary data is collected from Coimbatore employment exchange office, websites and magazines.

Tools used for Analysis

- Simple percentage analysis
- Rank analysis
- Likert scale analysis

Sample Size

- 120 Respondents.

Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling technique was used in this study.

Limitations of the Study

- The study is conducted in Coimbatore, so anything that explains awareness outside this area will be irrelevant.
- The respondents were limited and cannot be treated as a whole population.
- The respondents may be biased.
- The accuracy of indications given by the respondents may not be considered adequate.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Socio Economic Status of the Respondents

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Below 18 Years	10	8.30
18 Years - 25 Years	73	60.87
26 Years - 35 Years	24	20.00
Above 35 Years	13	10.83
Total	120	100

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	52	43.33
Female	68	56.67
Total	120	100
Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Up to 8th Standard	1	0.83
10th	3	2.50
12th	12	10.00
Diploma	16	13.35
Undergraduate	64	53.33
Postgraduate	23	19.16
Others	1	0.83
Total	120	100
Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Students	57	47.50
Government Employee	10	8.34
Private Employee	43	35.83
Unemployed	10	8.33
Total	120	100
Marital Status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Married	35	29.17
Unmarried	85	70.83
Total	120	100
Family Type	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Nuclear Family	87	72.50
Joint Family	33	27.50
Total	120	100
No. of dependents of their Family	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1 Person	14	11.67
2 Persons	33	27.50
3 Persons	41	34.16
4 Persons	17	14.17
Above 4 Persons	6	5.00
None	9	7.50
Total	120	100
Annual Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Below Rs.1,00,000	39	32.50
Rs.1,00,001 – Rs.3,00,000	35	29.18
Rs.3,00,001 – Rs.5,00,000	17	14.16
Above Rs.5,00,000	2	1.66
No Income	27	22.50
Total	120	100

Stay	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Urban	50	41.67
Semi-Urban	46	38.33
Rural	24	20.00
Total	120	100

Interpretation

Majority (60.87%) of the respondents are fall under the age group of 18 – 25 years, Majority (56.67%) of the respondents were female, Majority (53.33%) of the respondents had completed their under graduation, Majority (47.57%) of the respondents were students, Majority (70.83%) of the respondents were unmarried, Majority (72.57%) of the respondents live as nuclear family, Majority (34.16%) of the respondents dependents of a family size of 3 members, Majority (32.50%) of the respondent’s annual income lies less than 1 lakh, Majority (41.67%) of the respondents stay in their urban area.

About Employment Exchange

Aware About Employment Exchange

Aware about employment exchange	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	99	82.50
No	21	17.50
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 82.50 % of the respondents are aware of the employment exchange and 17.50 % of the respondents are not awareness about the employment exchange.

Registration about Employment Exchange

Registration	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Registered	80	66.67
Not Registered	40	33.33
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 66.67 % of the respondents have registered for their educational qualification under employment exchange and 33.33 % of the respondents have not registered under employment exchange of their educational qualification.

Enrollment Through Registration of Employment Exchange

Enrollment	No. of Respondents	Percentage
8th	15	12.5
10th	32	26.66

12th	19	15.85
Graduate	12	10.00
Postgraduate	2	1.66
Not Registered	40	33.33
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 12.5 % of the respondents have enrolled in 8th, 26.66 % of the respondents have enrolled in 10th, 15.85 % of the respondents have enrolled in 12th, 10 % of the respondents have enrolled in Undergraduate, 1.66 % of the respondents have enrolled in Postgraduate and 33.33 % of the respondents have not enrolled the Employment Registration.

Registration Mode Done By

Mode of Registration	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Through School	60	50.00
By Self-Registration	20	16.67
Not Registered	40	33.33
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 50 % of the respondents have registered for employment through school, 16.67 % of the respondents have registered by self-registration for employment and 33.33 % of the respondents have not registered under employment exchange.

Mode of Self-Registration Done By

Mode of self registration	No. of Respondents	Percentage
On-line	16	80
Employment Exchange office	4	20
Total	20	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 80 % of the respondents has registered themselves by self-registration through on-line, 20 % of the respondents has registered by employment exchange office directly.

Awareness Activities Done by Employment Exchange

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	24	20
No	96	80
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 20% of the respondents have aware about the activities done by employment exchange and 80% of the respondents have not aware about the activities done by employment exchange.

Awareness about Stipend Given for Registered Unemployed People

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	31	25.83
No	89	74.17
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 25.83 % of the respondents are aware about stipend given by employment exchange and 74.17 % of the respondents are not aware about the stipend given by the employment exchange for unemployed people.

Information Getting for Relevant Job Through Employment Exchange

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	22	18.34
No	28	23.33
May Be	70	58.33
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 18.34 % of the respondents said that they get relevant jobs through employment exchange, 23.33% of the respondents said that they do not get relevant jobs through employment exchange and 58.33 % of the respondents have no idea about it.

Registered in Employment Exchange to Get a Government Job

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	57	47.50
No	21	17.50
May Be	42	35.00
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 47.5 % of the respondents thinks that we need to register in employment exchange to get a Government job, 17.5 % of the respondents thinks that it is not compulsory to register in employment exchange to get a Government job and 35 of the respondents has no idea about it.

Respondents Expectations through Improvements

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Mobile Application for doing all activities	33	27.50
Alert for renewal	26	21.67
Choose field of core specialization	34	28.33
I don't want any changes	27	22.50
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is revealed that 27.5 % of the respondents want mobile application for employment registration and renewals, 21.67 % of the respondents want alert for renewals, 28.33 % of the respondents want choose field of core specialization, 22.50 % of the respondents do not want any changes.

Rank Analysis

The Karl Pearson's method is based on the assumption the population being studied is normal or when the shape of the distraction is not known, there is need for a measure of correlation that is need for correlation that involves no assumptions above the parameter of population.

It is possible to avoid making any assumptions above the population being studied by ranking the observation according to size and basing the calculation on the ranks rather than upon the originate observations. It does not matter in which way the items are ranked, items number one may be the largest or it may be smallest using rather than actual observation gives the coefficient rank correlation.

Formula

$$R = 1 - \frac{6\sum D^2}{N(N^2 - 1)}$$

Where,

R = Rank coefficient of correlation

D = Different of rank between paired items in two series

Rank Analysis

Factors	I	II	III	IV	V	Total	Rank
Jobs through Employment Registration	39(5)	20(4)	19(3)	4(2)	38(1)	378	II
Private Jobs	8(5)	34(4)	34(3)	25(2)	19(1)	347	IV
On – Campus Jobs	31(5)	17(4)	33(3)	19(2)	20(1)	380	I
Off – Campus Jobs	8(5)	34(4)	16(3)	37(2)	25(1)	323	V
Own – Business	34(5)	15(4)	18(3)	35(2)	18(1)	372	III

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table it is understood that on-campus jobs ranked as I, job through employment registration ranked as II, own-business ranked as III, private jobs ranked as IV and off- campus jobs ranked as V.

- It is revealed that on-campus jobs ranked first.

Likert Scale Analysis

A Likert scale is a method of measuring attitudes, ordinal scale of responses to a question or statement, ordered in hierarchical sequence from strongly negative to strongly positive. Used mainly in behavioral science and psychiatry. In Likert scale method, a person’s attitude is measured by combining (adding or averaging) their responses across all items.

Formula

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Likert scale} &= \sum (fx) / \text{Total number of respondents} \\ f &= \text{Number of respondents} \\ x &= \text{Likert scale value} \\ \sum (fx) &= \text{Total score} \end{aligned}$$

Mid value

Mid-value indicates the middle most value of the likert scale.

Satisfaction Level about Website Information

S. No.	Factors	No. Of Respondents	Linkert Scale Value	Total Score
1	Highly Satisfied	14	5	70
2	Satisfied	40	4	160
3	Neutral	41	3	123
4	Dissatisfied	17	2	34
5	Highly Dissatisfied	9	1	9
	Total	120	15	396

Source: Primary Data

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Likert scale} &= \sum (fx) / \text{Total number of respondents} \\ &= 396/120 \\ &= 3.3 \end{aligned}$$

Interpretation

Likert scale value is 3.3 is greater than the mid value (3). So the respondents are satisfied about the information present in websites.

**Satisfaction Level About
S Employment Exchange Registration Procedures**

S. No.	Factors	No. Of Respondents	Linkert Scale Value	Total Score
1	Highly Satisfied	8	5	40
2	Satisfied	33	4	132
3	Neutral	47	3	141
4	Dissatisfied	22	2	44
5	Highly Dissatisfied	10	1	10
	Total	120	15	367

Source: Primary Data

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Likert scale} &= \sum (fx) / \text{Total number of respondents} \\ &= 367/120 \\ &= 3.06 \end{aligned}$$

Interpretation

Likert scale value is 3.06 is greater than the mid value (3). So the respondents are satisfied towards the employment exchange registration procedures.

Findings

Percentage Analysis

- It is revealed that majority 60.87 % of respondents are in the age group of 18 -25.
- It is revealed that majority 56.67 % of respondents are female.
- It is revealed that majority 53.33 % of respondent's educational qualification is of Undergraduate level.
- It is revealed that majority 47.5 % of the respondent's occupation is Student.
- It is revealed that majority 70.83 % of the respondents are unmarried.
- It is revealed that majority 72.5 % of the respondent's family type is from Nuclear Family.
- It is revealed that majority 34.16 % of the respondents are having 3 Persons of dependents in their family.
- It is revealed that majority 32.5 % of the respondents has annual income of below Rs. 1,00,000.
- It is revealed that majority 41.67 % of the respondents are from Urban area.
- It is revealed that majority 82.5 % of the respondents has aware about the employment exchange.
- It is revealed that majority 66.67 % of the respondents have registered under employment exchange of their educational qualification.
- It is revealed that majority 33.33 % of the respondents have not enrolled in the employment registration.
- It is revealed that majority 50 % of the respondents have registered themselves through school.
- It is revealed that 80 % of the respondents has registered themselves by self-registration through on-line
- It is revealed that 80 % of the respondents have not aware about the activities done by employment exchange.
- It is revealed that majority 74.17 % of the respondents are not aware about the stipend given by the employment exchange.
- It is revealed that majority 58.33 % of the respondents have no idea about whether they get a relevant job in employment exchange.
- It is revealed that majority 47.5 % of the respondents think that it is necessary to register in employment exchange to get a Government job.
- It is revealed that majority 28.33 % of the respondents want choose field of core specialization for the jobs they get in employment exchange.

Rank Analysis

- On-campus jobs have ranked first by the respondents.

Likert Scale Analysis

- The Likert scale values are greater than the mid-value. The respondents are hence satisfied with the information present in the websites of Employment Exchange.
- The Likert scale values are greater than the mid-value. The respondents are hence satisfied with the Employment Exchange procedures.

Suggestion

- Employment registration has many procedures that is unaware among the respondents.
- The Government websites have more information's regarding the procedure and renewal of the information.
- Many of the people do not know that we can even register in employment exchange even if we fail in our exams, we may get jobs according to that.
- Many respondents have suggested that they need mobile application, alert for renewal, and choose the specialized core and Easy interface and proper alerts for all necessary information to each person.
- Many persons are interested in Government Jobs but they are not putting effort for it.
- Our Government is even giving stipend for the candidates of the registered ones with certain conditions and it can be improved a lot and can be made know to all.
- On the whole Government is performing many activities but there is lack of awareness among the people and public too want to take some interest in that and should follow the procedures for getting a Government Job.

Conclusion

The study is awareness about the employment registration among the public. The study was conducted through surveys and questionnaires were given to the public for their responses. Many respondents have no idea whether they get relevant jobs in employment exchange and whether we should register in employment exchange to get a Government job. From this study it is concluded that it is compulsory to register ourselves in employment exchange to get a job in Government and the relevant jobs are not assured. We get jobs according to the seniority level and we should properly update our profile for the jobs. Even if we fail in our educational qualification we can register ourselves in employment and we get relevant jobs according to our profile.

Reference

- A Study of Educational Unemployment in Live Register of Employment Exchange in India presented by Kiran Devi (2017)Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR) Vol-3, Issue-3, 2017 ISSN: 2454- 1362, <http://www.onlinejournal.in>
- Employment through employment exchanges: An econometric analysis of employment exchange data of Gujarat and Uttar Pradesh by Jayshree Chugh and Kirti Zankharia (2015) EPRA International Journal of Economics and Business Review Vol-3, Issue-8, August 2015.
- ASSOCHEM ECO PULSE STUDY (March 2009), "Relevance of Employment Exchanges in the New Millenium."
- Research methodology, second edition 2003- Gopal Lal Jain

Website

<https://www.google.co.in/h?q=employment+exchange&oq=employment&aqs=chrome.4.69i57j0j35i39l2j0l2.7369j0j8&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8>

<https://tnvelaivaaippu.gov.in/>

<http://www.tn.gov.in/employment>

<https://tnvelaivaaippu.gov.in/Empower/o.n/+exchange&oq=employment&aqs=chrome.4.69i57j0j35i39l2j0l2.7369j0j8&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8>

<https://tnvelaivaaippu.gov.in/>

<http://www.tn.gov.in/employment>

<https://tnvelaivaaippu.gov.in/Empower/>